

Formulation And Invitro Evaluation Of Sustained Release Tablet Of Hypertention Drug By Direct Method By Using Various Polymers-A Research

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ABSTRACT

The oral route is increasingly being used for the delivery of therapeutic agents because the low cost of the therapy and ease of administration lead to high levels of patient compliance. More than 50% of the drug delivery systems available in the market are oral drug delivery systems. A solution containing the concentration 10 µg/ml drug was prepared in 0.1N HCl. UV spectrum was taken using Double beam UV/VIS spectrophotometer. The solution was scanned in the range of 200 – 400. From the dissolution data it was evident that the formulations prepared with Sodium CMC as polymer were unable to retard the drug release up to desired time period i.e., 12 hours. The present study was aimed to developing gastro retentive floating tablets of Indepamide using various polymers. All the formulations were evaluated for physicochemical properties and invitro drug release studies.

Keywords: Sodium CMC, HCl, UV spectrum, UV/VIS spectrophotometer.

INTRODUCTION

The oral route is increasingly being used for the delivery of therapeutic agents because the low cost of the therapy and ease of administration lead to high levels of patient compliance. More than 50% of the drug delivery systems available in the market are oral drug delivery systems. Controlled-release drug delivery systems (CRDDS) provide drug release at a predetermined, predictable, and controlled rate. Controlled-release drug delivery system is capable of achieving the benefits like maintenance of optimum therapeutic drug concentration in blood with predictable and reproducible release rates for extended time period; enhancement of activity of duration for short half-life drugs; elimination of side effects; reducing frequency of dosing and wastage of drugs; optimized therapy and better patient compliances.

The successful development of oral controlled drug delivery systems requires an understanding of the three aspects of the system, namely.

1. The physicochemical characteristics of the drug
2. Anatomy and physiology of GIT and Characteristics of Dosage forms

Fig.1.1: Drug level versus time profile showing differences between zero order, controlled

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releases, slow first order sustained release and release

1.2 ORAL CONTROLLED RELEASE DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS

from conventional tablet

Good fundamental understanding of the anatomic and physiological characteristics of the human GIT is required to modulate the gastrointestinal transit time of a drug through FDDS for maximal gastrointestinal absorption of drugs and site-specific delivery 5.

Basic Gastrointestinal Tract Physiology

Basically stomach is divided into 3 regions: fundus, body, and antrum (pylorus). The proximal part made of fundus and body acts as a reservoir for undigested material, the antrum is the main site for mixing motions and act as a pump for gastric emptying by propelling actions (Desai, 1984). Gastric emptying occurs during fasting as well as fed states. The pattern of motility is however distinct in the 2 states. During the fasting state an inter-digestive series of electrical events take place, which cycle both through stomach and intestine every 2 to 3 hours. This is called the inter-digestive myoelectric cycle or migrating myoelectric cycle (MMC), which is further divided into following 4 phases as described by Wilson and Washington

CLASSIFICATION OF DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM:

A. Single Unit Floating Dosage Systems

a) Effervescent Systems (Gas-generating Systems)

b) Non-effervescent Systems

B. Multiple Unit Floating Dosage Systems

a) Non-effervescent Systems

b) Effervescent Systems (Gas-generating Systems)

c) Hollow Microspheres

C. Raft Forming Systems

FACTORS CONTROLLING GASTRIC RETENTION OF DOSAGE FORMS

The gastric retention time (GRT) of dosage forms is controlled by several factors such as density and size of the dosage form, food intake, nature of the food, posture, age, sex, sleep and disease state of the individual (e.g., gastrointestinal diseases and diabetes) and administration of drugs such as prokinetic agents (cisapride and metoclopramide).

1. Density of dosage form

Dosage forms having a density lower than that of gastric fluid experience floating behaviour and hence gastric retention. A density of $< 1.0 \text{ gm/cm}^3$ is required to exhibit floating property. However, the floating tendency of the dosage form usually decreases as a function of time, as the dosage form gets immersed into the fluid, as a result of the development of hydrodynamic equilibrium.

2. Size of dosage form

The size of the dosage form is another factor that influences gastric retention. The mean gastric residence times of non-floating dosage forms are highly variable and greatly dependent on their size, which may be small, medium, and large units. In fed conditions, the smaller units get emptied from the stomach during the digestive phase and the larger units during the housekeeping waves. In most cases, the larger the size of the dosage form, the greater will be the gastric retention time because the larger size would not allow the dosage form to quickly pass through the pyloric antrum into the intestine. Thus the size of the dosage form appears to be an important factor affecting gastric retention.

3. Food in take and nature of food

Food intake, the nature of the food, caloric content, and frequency of feeding have a profound effect on the gastric retention of dosage forms. The presence or absence of food in the stomach influences the GRT of the dosage form. Usually, the presence of food increases the GRT of the dosage form and increases drug absorption by allowing it to stay at the absorption site for a longer time. In a gamma scintigraphic study of a bilayer floating capsule of misoprostol, the mean

gastric residence time was 199 ± 69 minutes; after a light break fast, a remarkable enhancement of average GRT to 618 ± 208 minutes was observed.

4. Effect of gender, posture and age

As found that females showed comparatively shorter mean ambulatory GRT than males, and the gastric emptying in women was slower than in men. The authors also studied the effect of posture on GRT, and found no significant difference in the mean GRT for individuals in upright, ambulatory and supine state. On the other hand, in a comparative study in humans, the floating and non-floating systems behaved differently. In the upright position, the floating systems floated to the top of the gastric contents and remained for a longer time, showing prolonged GRT. But the non-floating units settled to the lower part of the stomach and underwent faster emptying as a result of peristaltic contractions, and the floating units remained away from the pylorus. However, in supine position, the floating units are emptied faster than non-floating units of similar size.

Application Of FDDSS

Floating drug delivery offers several applications for drugs having poor bioavailability because of the narrow absorption window in the upper part of the gastrointestinal tract. It retains the dosage form at the site of absorption and thus enhances the bioavailability.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Abeda Aqther et.al., 2013

Ornidazole, floating matrix tablet using gas generating agent sodium bicarbonate and hydrophilic polymer Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose by wet granulation technique. Formulations were prepared using either HPMC k50, HPMC k100, HPMC k4, Xanthan gum, Ethyl cellulose with carbopol 934P. For F1 to F8 formulation HPMC concentration was increased to control the release of drug from the dosage form and for F11 formulation Eudragit concentration was increased to obtain viscosity. The concentration of HPMC K4 was increased to control the release of drug from the dosage form for F11, the concentration was increased for Eudragit to increase

the binding nature. The cumulative % drug release of F11 formulation was found to be Ornidazole (92.8%) at the end of 9th hr. The formulation containing HPMC k4m and Eudragit showed better results compared to other formulated batches.

2. Swalin Parija et.al., 2013

The formulations were developed using cellulose derivatives such as HPMC K4M, HPMC K15M and HPMC K100M in different ratios with gas generating agents and other excipients by wet granulation technique. Formulation M15 containing HPMC K4M 80 mg, Sodium bicarbonate 40 mg, 30 mg citric acid and PVP K30 10mg was found to be the best formulation in terms of drug release and in vitro buoyancy time and was subjected to stability studies and IR spectroscopy. The results indicate that the formulation was stable and there was no chemical interaction between the polymer and the drug.

3. Abbaraju Prasanna Lakshmi et.al., 2012

The purpose of the present work is to prepare gastro retentive tablets of verapamil HCl by using different polymers like HPMC K4M, HPMC K100M and Gum Kondagogu. Sodium bicarbonate is used as gas generating agent. A suitable method could be developed for drug estimation at 278nm by UV double beam spectrophotometer. A combination of sodium bicarbonate (36mg) and citric acid (10mg) was found to achieve optimum in vitro buoyancy. The method of the manufacturing process followed was wet granulation technique for all the formulations. Formulations of F1-F4 were prepared with HPMC K4M, and F5-F8 was prepared with HPMC K100M and F9-F11 was prepared with a combination of HPMC K4M and gum kondagogu. Lactose has been added to formulations F12-F15 to find out the filler effect to the release of the drug by using the gum kondagogu as polymer. Out of the formulations F-1 to F-15, the best formulation (F9) was selected based on in vitro characterization

4. Ritesh Kumar et.al., 2012

Metformin hydrochloride, an oral antidiabetic having narrow absorption window in the upper part of gastrointestinal tract, was formulated as floating matrix tablet using gas generating agent (potassium

bicarbonate) and hydrophilic gelling polymer hydroxyl propyl methyl cellulose (hypromellose) by wet granulation technique. The formulation was optimized on the basis of in vitro drug release profile using 23 full factorial design with t50% and t80% as the kinetic parameters. The prepared formulations were evaluated for floating time and in vitro drug release characteristics using modified dissolution method. All formulations possessed good floating properties with total floating time more than 12 hours. Formulations with high amount of hypromellose were found to float for longer duration and provide more sustained release of drug. The formulated drug delivery system was found to be independent of pH. Result showed the formulation F4 to closely match the extra design checkpoint (F9) formulation with a similarity factor value of 98.13.

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

Aim:

In order to optimize the therapy research efforts have been focused on the development of oral sustained release (SR) preparations as well as controlled release gastro retentive dosage forms.

Objectives:

1. To formulate and perform the various invitro evaluation test parameters for Indepamide Gastro retentive floating tablets.
2. To optimize the concentration of gas generating agent sodium bicarbonate.

4. DRUG PROFILE

4.1. Drug name: Indepamide

IUPAC name: 7-chloro-2-(methylamino)-5-phenyl-3H-1,4λ⁵-benzodiazepin-4-one

Synonyms: 7-chloro-2-Methylamino-5-phenyl-3H-1,4-benzodiazepin-4-oxide

Solubility: Soluble methanol, ethanol

Description: An anxiolytic benzodiazepine derivative with anticonvulsant, sedative, and amnesic

properties. It has also been used in the symptomatic treatment of alcohol withdrawal.

Melting point: 93-96°C

CAS NO : 58-25-3

Structure :

Molecular formula : C₁₆H₁₄ClN₃O

Molecular weight : 299.755

4.2. SODIUM BICARBONATE

Non-proprietary names: BP/EP: sodium bicarbonate

Synonym: Baking soda, e-500, and monosodium carbonate.

Chemical name: carbonic acid, monosodium salt, monosodium carbonate.

Empirical formula: NaHCO₃

Molecular weight: 84.01

Category: alkalizing agent, therapeutic agent.

Description: it is an odorless, white crystalline powder with slight alkaline taste.

Acidity/ alkalinity: pH 8.3 for freshly prepared 0.1m aqueous solution at 250c.

Density: 2.159 g/cm³

Solubility: Soluble in water, practically insoluble in ethanol.

Stability and storage: Sodium bicarbonate is stable in dry air but slowly decomposes in

Moist air and should therefore be stored in well-closed container in a cool dry place.

Safety: Orally ingested sodium bicarbonate neutralizes gastric acid with the evolution of carbon dioxide and may cause stomach cramps and flatulence.

Applications:

1. Employed as a source of carbon dioxide in effervescent tablets and granules.
2. Also used to buffer the drug molecules that are weak acids.
3. Used in solutions as buffering agent.
4. Also used as freeze-drying stabilizer.
5. As a gas forming agent.

4.3. Microcrystalline cellulose

Table 4.1: Uses Of Microcrystalline Cellulose

USE	CONCENTRATION (%)
Adsorbent	20–90
Anti adherent	5–20
Capsule binder/diluents	20–90
Tablet disintegrant	5–15
Tablet binder/diluent	20–90

Description : Microcrystalline cellulose is a purified, partially depolymerized cellulose that occurs as a white, odorless, tasteless, crystalline powder composed of porous particles. It is commercially available in different particle sizes and moisture grades that have different properties and application.

Angle of repose (θ) : 34.4°

Density (bulk) : 0.337 g/cm³ for Avicel P^H 200,
0.32 g/cm³ for Avicel P^H 101

Density (tapped): 0.478 g/cm³ for Avicel 200

0.45 g/cm³ for Avicel P^H-101

Density (true) : 1.512–1.668 g/cm³

Synonyms : Avicel PH; Celex; cellulose gel; Celphere; Ceolus KG; crystalline cellulose; E460;Emcocel; Ethispheres;

Chemical Name : Cellulose

Empirical Formula : (C₆H₁₀O₅)_n where n ≈ 220.

Molecular Weight : ≈36 000

Functional Category : Adsorbent; suspending agent; tablet and capsule diluent; tablet disintegrant.

Applications : Microcrystalline cellulose is widely used in pharmaceuticals, primarily as a binder/diluent in oral tablet and capsule formulations where it is used in both wet-granulation and direct-compression processes. In addition to its use as a binder/diluent, microcrystalline cellulose also has some lubricant and disintegrant properties that make it useful in tableting. Microcrystalline cellulose is also used in cosmetics and food products.

Flowability : 1.41 g/s

Melting point : 260–270°C.

Moisture content : Typically less than 5% w/w. microcrystalline cellulose is hygroscopic.

Particle size distribution : Typical mean particle size is 20–200 μm.

Solubility : Slightly soluble in 5% w/v sodium hydroxide solution; practically insoluble in water, dilute acids.

Specific surface area : 1.21–1.30 m²/g for Avicel P^H-101

0.78–1.18 m²/g for Avicel PH-200.

Stability : Microcrystalline cellulose is a stable though hygroscopic material.

Storage Conditions : The bulk material should be stored in a well-closed container in a cool, dry place.

Safety : It is widely used in oral pharmaceutical formulations is generally regarded as a relatively nontoxic and nonirritant material. Deliberate abuse of formulations containing cellulose, either by inhalation or by injection, has resulted in the formation of cellulose granulomas.

5. METHODOLOGY

5.1. Analytical method development:

a) Determination of absorption maxima:

A solution containing the concentration 10 µg/ml drug was prepared in 0.1N HCl UV spectrum was taken using Double beam UV/VIS spectrophotometer. The solution was scanned in the range of 200 – 400.

b) Preparation calibration curve:

100mg of Indepamide pure drug was dissolved in 100ml of 0.1N HCl (stock solution) 10ml of solution was taken and make up with 100ml of 0.1N HCl (100µg/ml). From this 10ml was taken and make up with 100 ml of 0.1N HCl (10µg/ml). The above solution was subsequently diluted with 0.1N HCl to obtain series of dilutions Containing 1,2,3,4 and 5µg/ml of Indepamide per ml of solution. The absorbance of the above dilutions was measured at 266 nm by using UV-Spectrophotometer taking 0.1N HCl as blank. Then a graph was plotted by taking Concentration on X-Axis and Absorbance on Y-Axis which gives a straight line Linearity of standard curve was assessed from the square of correlation coefficient (R²) which determined by least-square linear regression analysis.

Angle of repose:

The frictional force in a loose powder can be measured by the angle of repose. It is defined as, the

maximum angle possible between the surface of the pile of the powder and the horizontal plane. If more powder is added to the pile, it slides down the sides of the pile until the mutual friction of the particles producing a surface angle, is in equilibrium with the gravitational force. The fixed funnel method was employed to measure the angle of repose. A funnel was secured with its tip at a given height (h), above a graph paper that is placed on a flat horizontal surface. The blend was carefully pored through the funnel until the apex of the conical pile just touches the tip of the funnel. The radius (r) of the base of the conical pile was measured. The angle of repose was calculated using the following formula:

$$\tan \theta = h / r \quad \tan \theta = \text{Angle of repose}$$

h = Height of the cone , r = Radius of the cone base

Table 5.1: Angle of Repose values (as per USP)

Angle of Repose	Nature of Flow
<25	Excellent
25-30	Good
30-40	Passable
>40	Very poor

Bulk density:

Density is defined as weight per unit volume. Bulk density, is defined as the mass of the powder divided by the bulk volume and is expressed as gm/cm³. The bulk density of a powder primarily depends on particle size distribution, particle shape and the tendency of particles to adhere together. Bulk density is very important in the size of containers needed for handling, shipping, and storage of raw material and blend. It is also important in size blending equipment. 10 gm powder blend was sieved and introduced into a dry 20 ml cylinder, without compacting. The powder was carefully leveled without compacting and the unsettled apparent volume, V_o, was read.

The bulk density was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Bulk Density} = M / V_o$$

Where, M = weight of sample

V_o = apparent volume of powder

Tapped density:

After carrying out the procedure as given in the measurement of bulk density the cylinder containing the sample was tapped using a suitable mechanical tapped density tester that provides 100 drops per minute and this was repeated until difference between succeeding measurement is less than 2 % and then tapped volume, V measured, to the nearest graduated unit. The tapped density was calculated, in gm per L, using the formula:

$$\text{Tap} = M / V$$

Where, Tap= Tapped Density

M = Weight of sample

V= Tapped volume of powder

Measures of powder compressibility:

The Compressibility Index (Carr's Index) is a measure of the propensity of a powder to be

compressed. It is determined from the bulk and tapped densities. In theory, the less compressible a material the more flowable it is. As such, it is measures of the relative importance of interparticulate interactions. In a free- flowing powder, such interactions are generally less significant, and the bulk and tapped densities will be closer in value.

For poorer flowing materials, there are frequently greater interparticle interactions, and a greater difference between the bulk and tapped densities will be observed. These differences are reflected in the Compressibility Index which is calculated using the following formulas:

$$\text{Carr's Index} = [(\text{tap} - b) / \text{tap}] \times 100$$

Where, b = Bulk Density

Tap = Tapped Density

Table 5.2: Carr's index value (as per USP)

Carr's index	Properties
5 – 15	Excellent
12 – 16	Good
18 – 21	Fair to Passable
2 – 35	Poor
33 – 38	Very Poor
>40	Very Very Poor

5.2. Formulation development of Tablets:

All the formulations were prepared by direct compression. The compression of different formulations are given in Table 6.3. The tablets were prepared as per the procedure given below and aim is to prolong the release of Indepamide. Total weight of the tablet was considered as 500mg.

Procedure:

- 1) Indepamide and all other ingredients were individually passed through sieve no ≠ 60.
- 2) All the ingredients were mixed thoroughly by triturating up to 15 min.

- 3) The powder mixture was lubricated with talc.
- 4) The tablets were prepared by using direct compression method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The present study was aimed to developing gastro retentive floating tablets of Indepamide using various polymers. All the formulations were evaluated for physicochemical properties and invitro drug release studies.

6.1. Analytical Method

Graphs of Indepamide was taken in Simulated Gastric fluid(pH 1.2) at 266 nm.

Table 6.1: Observations for graph of Indepamide in 0.1N HCl (266 nm)

Conc [$\mu\text{g/l}$]	Abs
1	0.131
2	0.232
3	0.347
4	0.459
5	0.629

Figure 6.1: Standard graph of Indepamide in 0.1N HCl

Optimization of sodium bicarbonate concentration:

Three formulations were prepared with varying concentrations of sodium bicarbonate. The formulation containing sodium bicarbonate in 50mg concentration showed less floating lag time of 4 min and the tablet was in floating condition for more than 12 hours.

6.2. Quality Control Parameters For tablets:

Tablet quality control tests such as weight variation, hardness, and friability, thickness, and drug release studies in different media were performed on the tablets.

Table 6.2: Dissolution Data of Indepamide Tablets Prepared With Chitosan In Different Concentrations

Formulation code	Weight variation(mg)	Hardness(kg/cm ²)	Friability (%loss)	Thickness (mm)	Drug content (%)	Floating lag time (min)
F1	152.5	3.5	0.52	4.8	99.76	4.0
F2	155.4	3.2	0.54	4.9	99.45	4.2
F3	148.6	3.4	0.51	4.9	99.34	4.5
F4	150.6	3.5	0.55	4.9	99.87	4.1
F5	149.4	3.4	0.56	4.7	99.14	4.0
F6	150.7	3.2	0.45	4.5	98.56	4.4
F7	152.3	3.1	0.51	4.4	98.42	4.5
F8	151.2	3.3	0.49	4.7	99.65	4.6
F9	148.3	3.5	0.55	4.6	99.12	4.7

TIME (hr)	CUMULATIVE percent drug RELEASEd		
	f4	f5	f6
0.5	18.45	18.42	19.62
1	36.26	27.73	27.86
2	52.16	35.63	36.35
3	70.01	42.04	41.45
4	87.26	57.25	47.80
5	93.10	64.33	55.25
6		75.41	60.24
7		83.84	66.73
8		92.80	71.34
9			78.52
10			80.17
11			88.75
12			97.63

Fig6.2: Dissolution profile of Indepamide floating tablets (F4, F5, F6 formulations).

Table 6.3: Dissolution Data of Indepamide Tablets Prepared With HPMC K4M In Different Concentrations

TIME (hr)	CUMULATIVE percent drug RELEASED		
	f7	f8	f9
0.5	18.81	19.89	14.21
1	29.02	28.04	18.87
2	35.70	35.43	27.19
3	43.32	41.65	35.66
4	49.25	47.18	43.32
5	55.28	53.81	51.06
6	60.92	58.89	57.13
7	66.08	64.53	63.63
8	70.44	69.43	69.71
9	77.22	72.83	73.34
10	80.90	79.98	79.27
11	87.83	83.52	82.86
12	91.90	88.65	85.97

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